

Grain quality

Mode of grain shattering in rice

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Shedding or shattering of grain in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) during harvesting to threshing sometimes causes major losses (Ramiah and Rao in 1953 reported 5 to 12%). This genetic characteristic of a variety is important to breeders.

To estimate the percentage of shattering in rice, a study was undertaken in 1977 and 1979 kharif of a sample of 121 popular cultivars grown in Madhya Pradesh. A uniform fall method (device from the Philippines) was adopted for each panicle and an average of 15 panicles/variety was used.

The study showed that local paddy No. 20 had no grain shattering and BD 6-1, MTU19, Bangoli-5, CO13, and GS19 had comparatively high percentages (26-29%). The maximum grain-shedding effect (up to 38%) was

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recorded in HR19.

The figure indicates that the majority of the varieties (68.6%) came between the range of 1 to 5 and 6 to 10% grain shattering. These varieties may be useful to the breeding program. ■

variety (142 cm) that is popular among farmers. It has fine grains (1,000-grain wt is 16.8 g) and is aromatic. It matures in 135-140 days and yields about 3.7 t/ha. It is erect and produces 6-8 panicles/hill (each panicle, is about 28 cm long with 205 grains/panicle). Kalimooch 64 is weakly photoperiod sensitive with good tolerance for blast and is resistant to the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*. ■

Role of resistant varieties in depressing brown planthopper populations in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam

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Since 1971, the brown planthopper (BPH) has been the most serious insect pest in the Mekong Delta. BPH-resistant varieties such as TN73-2, IR26, and IR30 partly reduced the BPH damage in the area. Since 1976, BPH biotype 2 which is capable of attacking the biotype 1-resistant varieties has become predominant.

During 1977 and early 1978, BPH attacks with resulting hopperburn and ragged stunt virus were severe in large rice areas. Screening for varieties resistant to biotype 2 began in late 1976, immediately after the biotype was detected. New rice varieties with resistance to biotype 2 — NN3A (IR36) and NN5A (IR2071-179-3) — were released by the end of 1977 after 1.5 years of testing and multiplying on experimental farms. They were planted widely in the areas most severely damaged by the insect.

The BPH populations in those areas remained below the economic threshold. After those two varieties, others resistant to BPH biotype 2 were identified and tested (see table). Since then, the farmers no longer accepted rice varieties susceptible to BPH, except in the deepwater areas where only traditional floating rice varieties can grow.

Today, the BPH is not a constraint to rice production in the Mekong Delta. Resistant varieties are an important component in the integrated control

Insect resistance

A new source of gall midge resistance

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Host plant resistance to the gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* offers distinct advantages to farmers compared to other methods of control, but few resistance donors have been identified: PTB10, PTB18, PTB21 from Kerala, India; Iswarkora from Andhra Pradesh, India; Leuang 152 from Thailand; Siam 29 from Indonesia; and OBS 677 from Sri Lanka.

A new source of resistance to gall midge — Kalimooch 64 — was

identified during field evaluation of genetic stock at CRRS during gall midge epidemics in 1972-73, 1975-76, and 1978-79.

The F₁ of Sona/Kalimooch and Jaya/Kalimooch 64 crosses exhibited 100% field resistance during the endemic year 1973. It is assumed that Kalimooch 64 may have a dominant gene for resistance, whereas the resistance from most of the donors reported earlier was recessive. The F₂ segregates escaped the 1974 epidemic; therefore further inheritance studies could not be summarized. However, advanced-generation selections exhibited 100% field resistance to gall midge.

Kalimooch 64 is an indigenous tall